

BlueGreen
Governance

WP6: Management

Task N° 6.1

BLUEGREEN GOVERNANCE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (Version: 1.0)

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ABBREVIATIONS

API	Application Programming Interface
BGG	BlueGreen Governance
CC	Creative Commons
CS	Case Study
CIA	Cumulative Impact Assessment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	European Digital Twin of the Ocean
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
MP3 MPEG-1	Audio Layer 3
MPEG-4	Moving Pictures Expert Group 4
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative protocol for metadata Harvesting
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent identifier
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
RDM	Research Data Management
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise SSH Secure Shell
WP	Work Package

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1. PROJECT OVERVIEW

The main goal of BlueGreen Governance (BGG) is to develop innovative land-sea governance schemes based on scientific evidence and societal choices that link marine policies with the management of the land and inland waters; and draw lessons on how to trigger and facilitate institutional change and policy reforms for better marine policies. The project responds to the need for better-informed decision-making processes, social engagement and digital innovation while promoting more harmonious and effective science-policy-society interfaces. The promotion of better science-policy, science-society and society-policy interactions will be embedded in the digital transformation and application of e-governance tools for codesign and service delivery.

Therefore, BGG develops in four steps. First, the project identifies existing barriers to effective marine governance and policy and defines which enablers can be used to overcome such barriers. Second, the project co-develops innovations and improvements in governance schemes. Third, the project puts potential innovative solutions into practice and tests their feasibility and viability through policy dialogues at the relevant territorial level. Fourth, the project identifies specific strategies and actions to translate niche experiences into common practices. The project also develops recommendations and instruments for capacity building so that new schemes of governance are sustainable beyond the duration of the project. Stakeholders from the territories investigated in the project as well as national, EU and international key actors are involved in all four groups of activities.

The impact pursued by BGG is to re-design marine policies around the land-sea connection and ease the implementation of EU and national marine policies and restore marine and coastal habitats taking into account climate change and land-sea interactions. Moreover, strategic foresight and deliberative planning will converge into a BGG Dashboard that aims at, firstly, integrating existing e-governance tools and data sources to support scientific prediction on the future and, secondly, including societal expectations, needs and concerns through stakeholder engagement and deliberation.

In terms of Case Studies, BGG will implement and assess these innovative governance schemes in 8 cases across several European regions and sea basins and will draw lessons on how to trigger and facilitate effective institutional change via capacity building. The cases are: Comunidad Valenciana; North Adriatic; the Solent; Western Scheldt; Oslofjord; Canary Islands and Reunion. With this geographical scope, the project will investigate five marine basins (Western Mediterranean Sea, Eastern Mediterranean Sea, North Sea, Atlantic Ocean and Indian Ocean), including one transnational marine basin (i.e. the North Adriatic case) and one transnational river basin (i.e. the Western Scheldt case).

Our consortium is made of 9 partner organisations from ten European countries and is balanced with representatives from academia and research institutions.

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2. PURPOSE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The purpose of the BlueGreen Governance (BGG) Data Management Plan (DMP) is to design and implement best practices for managing research data. This DMP outlines the key aspects of the research outputs' lifecycle, including publications and data, from the project's outset. The plan addresses topics such as data provenance, organization and curation, provisions for data access, preservation, sharing, and eventual deletion. Creating a DMP is integral to the research methodology, ensuring efficient data management, saving time, safeguarding information, and enhancing the impact and value of data for beneficiaries and other stakeholders during and after the project.

Research data management is a multidisciplinary field involving various stakeholders, including data creators who are experts in their research fields, database designers, data stewards to support DMP implementation, project managers, and IT support staff.

This DMP is a dynamic document, updated throughout the project and shared with all partners. The initial version (D6.1) is produced in Month 6 of the BlueGreen Governance project timeline and will be refined as the project progresses and more detailed information becomes available. Updates will be made following milestones such as new data generation, feedback from the consortium or external reviews, and new insights and best practices from collaboration and networking.

Furthermore, the DMP describes the main dimensions of data management and curation. Specifically, the DMP is designed to ensure adherence to FAIR principles (by, for example, promoting interoperability through the use of metadata standards or facilitating data sharing, amongst other aspects). All the datasets included in the DMP will be deposited in an open repository (Zenodo) and linked to the DMP.

3. DATA SUMMARY

The objective of this chapter is to provide a summary overview of the different types of data and information being used in BlueGreen Governance. These includes existing data sources and new data being generated by the project. This chapter will be updated and enriched as the implementation of the project progresses.

BlueGreen Governance will deal with data from a variety of sources:

- Data from external agents such as Copernicus, Datasets from Institutions, etc.
- Experimental or empirical data: The research may generate primary data sets, results from surveys, measurements, observations, interview transcripts, thematic analysis, case narratives, etc.
- Secondary data analysis: Results could include statistical analyses, predictive models, reinterpretations of previous data, etc.
- Theoretical or conceptual models: mathematical models, new or revised theories, conceptual frameworks, etc.
- Software or tool development: source code, user manuals, technical documentation, etc.

In the following paragraphs we provide some preliminary information on the sources and type of data that is expected to be (re)used and generated during the project. More information will be provided as the project is being implemented (see also Table 3).

Work Package 1 (WP1) will mostly conduct a systematic literature, and hence reuse secondary data, specifically of (English speaking) scientific research articles that are relevant for the framework developed in BGG. In collaboration with some Case Studies, WP1 might also collect some data from semi-structured interviews providing information on the history of governance schemes in some of the pilot areas.

Work Package 2 (WP2) will use data from innovative governance schemes and strategic foresight to feed the development of an e-governance tool referred to as the **BlueGreen Governance Dashboard (BGG Dashboard)** (figure 1.1) that will support the co-design of policy initiatives, thus functioning as an important component in the overall project. The BGG Dashboard will be designed to be able to be integrated with different stakeholder deliberation tools, to ensure that it is more widely applicable throughout Europe. As depicted in figure 1.1, the BGG Dashboard will be capable of taking in data from relevant open data sources (such as Copernicus data) and EU sources (namely data sets from the Joint Research Centre), and be integrated with existing digital tools used for cumulative impact appraisal (e.g., indicators/index-based methods, Multi Criteria Decision Analysis), scenario analysis and stakeholder engagement, such as Panorama's open source SeaSketch. Furthermore, strong interactions of the BGG Dashboard with the **Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO)** will be ensured throughout the project development. These interactions will potentially work as a two-way linkage since BGG can not only benefit from the DTO during the execution of the project but also contribute to it.

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Figure 1: The BlueGreen Governance Dashboard (preliminary draft)

Source: Grant Agreement BGG

The methods used for the co-design of innovative governance schemes in WP2 will be established through a semi-normative collaborative governance modelling approach: knowledge from the systematic literature review (WP1) will be integrated and complemented by an analysis of best practices for governance modelling. It will also be based on a combination of different methods used in strategic foresight, such as horizon scanning and megatrend analysis:

- Horizon scanning involves searching and investigation of signs of change in the present and their possible future repercussions. Horizon scanning is the basis of any strategic foresight process. It may involve desk research, expert surveys and review of existing literature.
- Megatrend analysis, the exploration and review of large-scale changes occurring in the present at the intersection of multiple policy domains, with complex and multidimensional implications for the future.
- Cumulative Impact Assessment (CIA) will be used to explore the expected effects induced by multiple pressures on the land-sea environment, focusing on critical interactions affecting the biodiversity-water-climate nexus through vulnerable receptors (e.g., ecosystems, tourism, agricultural production, water supply, etc.).

Work Package 3 (WP3) and **Work Package 4 (WP4)** will have an interactive research approach with a wide range of stakeholders, which will offer us new relevant data. However, the research is led by scientific organizations to ensure independence from vested interests. More specifically, WP3 will use a Deliberation Matrix to guide different workshops with institutions and key stakeholders in all case studies and in different stages of the project. Hence, the data collected will mostly be recordings of interviews, transcripts or minutes of recording, and summaries or notes on document analysis. WP4 will combine exploratory interviews with policy makers and academics along with document analysis (both academic literature and grey literature).

In the same way, and apart from the open data at European level, data obtained from the different study areas, at local and national level, will also be identified and examined in order to interrelate them with all the study methods described above.

In addition to all the aforementioned, we will also exchange impressions and data with other European projects of our same cluster, in order to jointly come up with more innovative and profitable solutions for the future.

Concerning the choice of **file formats**, it is important to publish using open and interoperable formats where possible. This allows greater data reusability and is not dependent on the purchase of a proprietary software license to reuse the data. Often, the most important file format to consider for long-term storage is either the original 'raw' file, or else a lossless file format directly converted from this original 'raw' file.

The research results from the project will be primarily digital. The data format should consider open, well-documented and non-proprietary formats whenever possible. Long and short-term formats, dissemination and preservation formats must be assessed depending on the purpose, whether to analyse, store and share. This data will be in highly compatible formats. Table 1 shows the suggested list of data types and formats recommended for Blue Green Governance. The list will be reviewed and updated during the project.

Table 1: Resume of digital categories and formats

Data type	Format
Graphics	jpeg, odg, pdf, png, ptx
Tables	odsu, opj, xlsx, .csv
Text	docx, pdf, txt, odt
Audio	flic, mp3
Video	mp4, ogv, ogg, mj2
Spatial Data	Shapefiles (.shp), GeoTIFFs (.tif), GeoJSON (.geojson), KML/KMZ (.kml, .kmz), GML (.gml), File Geodatabases (.gdb), Spatialite (.sqlite), NetCDF (.nc), GRIB (.grb), Web Map Services (WMS), Web Feature Services (WFS), MapInfo files (.tab)

Source: own elaboration

The **size of the data** is currently unknown. This aspect will be reviewed following this initial data management plan based on initial experiences storing the results of the different types of measurements but a large amount of storage is foreseen.

BlueGreen Governance will be collected and generated to:

1. Obtain information
2. Share information
3. Keep on record
4. Make informed decisions
5. Combine with other data

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The BGG **data may be useful** for independent researchers to better understand the content and conclusions of scientific publications which base their findings on the data. In addition, independent researchers might be able to use the files to produce figures and publications and make comparisons of their own results with the results in the data. Scientists might also use the data files to repeat the experiments and measurements to verify and validate the research. Moreover, decision makers and education institutions could be interested in the BGG's results. Finally, science writers and the press might also use the datasets to produce high-quality infographics that demonstrate the potential impact of the technology.

In terms of **publications**, results and data generated by this project will have the potential to support very relevant scientific publications. It is expected that the data collected, analyses performed, and findings obtained will contribute to knowledge in the field of governance and the physical and marine environment. These results could be published in highly visible peer-reviewed open access scientific journals, presented at academic conferences and shared with the scientific community through other means of scholarly communication.

4. FAIR PRINCIPLES

The FAIR principles of “Findability”, “Accessibility”, “Interoperability” and “Reusability” are at the core of the BlueGreen Governance data management plan and is discussed in this chapter. BGG will pay careful attention to the management of data to make sure they are findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, but also comply with national and EU rules and laws on personal data and data security.

Digital tools and skills for FAIR and open science are key enablers for the implementation of the new European Research Area, enhancing collaboration that will in turn accelerate research and innovation, as well as increase trust in science to be conducted with and for society (EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, 2021). The EC report “Turning FAIR into Reality” (European Commission DG Research and Innovation, 2018) concludes that FAIR digital objects (including software) need to be supported by FAIR services that provide persistent identifiers, metadata specifications, stewardship and repositories, actionable policies and Output Management Plans. All of these need to be created for FAIR software, to complement the significant FAIR initiatives that primarily encompass data, and to leverage existing efforts to enable this for software.

BGG will follow the FAIR principles of data sharing for data use during the course of the project and beyond as described in the following sections.

4.1. Findability

To make data findable, including provisions for metadata, a DOI will be issued for the BGG Community in Zenodo, as well as to every published record on it.

Metadata of each record will be indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo’s search engine immediately after publishing. Zenodo’s default scheme is DataCite <https://schema.datacite.org/>. When uploading any repository to Zenodo, the repository metadata will be populated according to the DataCite metadata scheme. This ensures consistency and interoperability of data stored in Zenodo with other repositories and services that also use the DataCite metadata standard. Moreover, Zenodo uses standardised vocabulary and provides keywords and subjects (see EuroSciVoc: <https://op.europa.eu/es/web/eu-vocabularies/euroscivoc>).

Also, the following actions will be taken to make data findable:

- Data and metadata will be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier, a DataCite Digital Object Identifier (DOI);
- Data will be described with rich standard metadata in multiple human- and machine- readable formats (defined by the reusable principles);
- Metadata will clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes;
- Data and metadata will be registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

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4.2 Accessibility

Project deliverables, reports, presentations, workshop contents, datasets etc. will be deposited on Zenodo and linked to a 'Zenodo community' named after the project for easy access. Recordings of public events will be shared and made available on the BGG website. Pictures and videos of participants will only be taken with explicit permission from participants. All collected and developed data will be made publicly available as soon as possible.

During the project, the different deliverables and progress of the case studies will be published on the already launched **project website** (<https://bggovernance.eu>).

Additionally, important findings will be published at **Open Research Europe**.

The default repository of the Horizon-BlueGreen Governance project for depositing data, new knowledge, and tools is Zenodo (<https://www.zenodo.org/>). Zenodo uses JSON Schema (<https://json-schema.org>). Zenodo is a European Commission co-founded repository for publications and data. In addition, DOI is automatically assigned to all Zenodo documents. Both are compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon Europe program and OpenAire initiative. In this regard, Zenodo has defined access conditions and possible restrictions, and conforms to OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) collection protocols.

Zenodo is widely recognised as a trusted source for scientific and academic research. It is supported by leading research organisations, including CERN, and uses robust data management and security practices to ensure the integrity and reliability of the data stored on its platform. In addition, Zenodo adheres to internationally recognised standards in terms of digital preservation and open access.

Zenodo resolves the identifiers assigned to the documents deposited in its platform to digital objects. For example, when accessing a DOI assigned to a document in Zenodo, the system automatically resolves this identifier to the corresponding digital object, allowing users to directly access the document or dataset. Additionally, it offers full data versioning support. This allows researchers to deposit multiple versions of their data and documents on the platform. Each version is clearly identified and labelled, making it easy to track and manage. Users can access previous versions of data and compare changes between versions to maintain transparency and reproducibility in scientific research.

Operating data, raw data from the different surveys or interviews carried out during the whole project and personal data of the survey or interviews participants will be restricted to the members of the research project and will only be accessible according to the established accessibility levels. The Consortium will establish the criteria for access that data and manage its application (see Responsibilities section). Access to such data will be selected on a case-by-case basis. Ethical aspects and data security, including intellectual property requirements, will be considered. If necessary, some or all data may be withheld for possible publication.

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The project recognises the necessity of full access embargoes if any security or commercialisation matters apply. Outside those cases, all data are handled in compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) principles using standard ontologies and accepted metadata.

Once processing, quality control, organisation, analysis and publication have been completed, the data will be made accessible through deposit in Zenodo. All data associated with the project's scientific publications will be made openly available by default, unless there is a specific reason not to publish them. For example, data obtained with the permission of third parties but who have not given permission to make the data publicly available.

Strategies to minimize open access restrictions may include anonymizing or aggregating data, obtaining participant consent for data sharing, and securing copyright permissions. If BGG partners do not fully own the intellectual property rights, third-party licenses should be reviewed to verify usage conditions and licensing of the data. In some cases, BGG partners may need to obtain permissions from third parties to make the data available. Relevant attribution information for the original creators will be recorded in the metadata. If the dataset still has open access restrictions imposed by third parties, a metadata record should still be created. Instead of linking to the open access dataset, the metadata will link to a point of contact for requesting access to the data. Such data should use an alternative non-open license. Any non-open licenses used will be included in this DMP.

4.3. Interoperability

Zenodo assigns persistent identifiers to all datasets and results deposited on its platform. It uses DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to uniquely identify each digital object. Zenodo's DOIs are managed by DataCite, an internationally recognised metadata standards compatible with automatic harvesting, such as OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting). All these guarantees the persistence and interoperability of the data with other digital object identification systems.

In case it is unavoidable to use uncommon vocabularies and the project needs to generate its own specific vocabulary, mappings to more commonly used ontologies/vocabularies or additional explanations will be provided together with the data in order to allow interoperability across disciplines and to allow reusing, refining and extending them.

The following actions will be taken to make data interoperable:

- data and metadata will use an accessible, shared, and broadly applicable programming language;
- data and metadata will use standard, globally controlled vocabularies that follow FAIR principles;
- data and metadata will include qualified references to other data and metadata; and
- data and metadata will be published in formats ensuring interoperability.

4.4. Reusability

BlueGreen Governance will intensively reuse existing data.

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Table 2 provides a first overview of the different kinds of data that will be reused in different Work Packages and Case Studies, the type and formats of the data reused, the purpose of data re-use, the size and origin of that such data and its utility outside the project.

Table 2: BGG data re-use

WP	Reuse of existing data and reasons for it	Types and formats to generate or re-use	Purpose of the data generation or re-use	Expected size of the data	Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used	Data utility (usefulness), outside the project
WP1 (KU Leuven)	The systematic literature review builds on the reuse of secondary data, specifically of (English speaking) scientific research articles that are relevant for the framework we developed.	Data types and formats generated: 1) bibliographic references managed in Zotero (.pdf or .docx format) for the systematic literature review; 2) observational data from digital audio files of interviews (.wav or other format); 3) pseudonymized transcripts of the <u>audiofiles</u> of the interviews in digital format (.docx, .rtf or other); 4) notes taken during data collection of the interviews (.docx); 5) bibliographic references on additional documents (articles, reports from <u>CROSSgov</u> , etc.) as reference for an argument in the analysis; 6) notes (.pdf or .docx or other) taken during the processing of these bibliographic references; 7) qualitative data analysis documents in NVivo or Excel (.xlsx or <u>.nvp</u> or other) from the coding of the articles in the SLR and of the interviews; 8) notes taken during the data collection process on the steps in/flow of the SLR process (.docx or other) including keywords and screening criteria and their <u>justification</u> ; 9) coding schemes developed during the data collection and analysis process (.docx or other) that were used for conducting the systematic literature review. In addition, types and format for reuse data includes digital copies of the scientific articles located via two existing databases in .pdf format for the SLR.	Collecting the necessary qualitative materials for completion of the tasks in WP1: conducting a systematic literature review and complementing these insights via specific information offered by case study leaders/stakeholders via questionnaires, interviews, focus groups or other means. Other purposes are ensuring the quality of data collection and analysis methods and enabling transparency and replication.	> 1 GB	Reuse of scientific articles for the SLR located and <u>retrieved</u> via Web of Science and Scopus, as well as via KU Leuven <u>Limo-Libis</u> integrated search interface	The data are useful and relevant in a marine governance context, even beyond the scope of the BGG project. They are generated and saved in an open, accessible (understandable) and <u>transparent</u> manner.

Blue Green Governance

Deliverable 6.1.Data Management Plan

WP2 (UPSACLAY)	Use of COPERNICUS and EMODNET datasets to develop the dashboard in order to represent the current situation in terms of risks and vulnerabilities in relation to the Climate Change - Water - Biodiversity nexus. Possible use of datasets develops at CS levels	Data sets	To represent the current situation in terms of risks and vulnerabilities and to inform scenarios develop at EU and CS levels	> 1Go	COPERNICUS (EU), EMODNET (EU); CS	until 2 years after the end of the project
WP3 (CMCC)	Use of the Deliberation Matrix within workshops at CS levels	Recordings of interviews; transcripts or minutes of recording; summaries and notes on document analysis	To compare scenarios in terms of governance processes	<1Go	CS	until 2 years after the end of the project
WP4 (OUNL)	(Jan-June 2024) Exploratory interviews with Flemish policy makers and academics on flood protection in the Sea Scheldt, and document analysis (both academic literature and grey literature)	Recordings of interviews; transcripts or minutes of recording; summaries and notes on document analysis	Audio- and Word-files	-	Not foreseen	until 2 years after the end of the project
WP5 (SK)	unknow	unknow	unknow	unknow	unknow	unknow
WP6 (UV)	Data collected during the BGG proposal preparation and GA preparation will be re-used for project management and coordination overall.	Generate contact lists for internal communicational, project outputs (e.g. deliverables, reports and presentations) and all data needed for financial and technical reporting. Formats: .XLSX, .DOCX, .PPTX, .PDF, Photo Format, Video Format.	Ensure an efficient communication flow within the consortium. Share project results publicly beyond the consortium. Ensure proper administrative and financial project management.	It will vary depending on the type of data, but they are expected to be in the (low) hundreds of MB, while potential video files can be in GB.	Both, generated and re-used, but mostly generated.	Public project outputs such as deliverables, presentations, and reports about the project or activities carried out in the project can be relevant to the wider citizen science community, and to other organisations implementing or planning a project with similar characteristics.

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CS	Short data description, aim of the data and relevance for the project	Type of data	Data format	Reuse of any existing data	Relevance outside the project	Expected size	Storage period
CS 1 (Valencian, Community, Spain)	Jan- June 2024: Exploratory workshop with Spanish policy makers, civil society, NGOs and academics on wetlands/CV's CS	Recordings of interviews; transcripts or minutes of recording; summaries and notes on document analysis	Audio (both English and Spanish/Valencian language) and word/pdf files	no	first approach to the project's focus groups, evaluation and impact assessment	>1GB	until 2 years after the end of the project
CS 2 (North Adriatic, Italy and Slovenia)	Collection of relevant spatial (GIS) datasets for the case study area. Including pan-European data and national datasets.	Vector spatial data; raster spatial data	shapefiles; geopackage; geoTIFF;	CorineLandCover 2018; Natura 2000 areas; digital elevation model; sea depth digital model; Slovenian national datasets (nature; infrastructure; protected areas; habitat monitoring)	We will do some post processing, analysing and visualization of the existing datasets. The resulting layers and methodology can be useful for other areas.	< 2 GB	Main project results will be published in Zenodo with unlimited storage period. Main result will also be stored at the partner institution for at least 10 years.
CS 3 (The Solent, UK)	Jan- Sept 2024 to 2027: Interviews with stakeholders, policy makers, civil societies, NGOs and academics on essential fish habitats (EFH), and how coastal governance is important / connected to terrestrial systems. Ecological data will also be collected of the EFH to determine level of nature-based solutions (NBS) and biodiversity net gain (BNG).	Recordings of interviews; transcripts or minutes of recording; summaries and notes on document analysis. Ecological data (percent surface area of EFH, density, habitat complexity, species abundance and diversity).	Audio, and Excel / Word.doc files.		To feed into the decision-making, policy and management of the loW UNESCO Biosphere	?	To be defined in agreement with the consortium partners.
CS 4 (Western Scheldt, Belgium)	(Jan-June 2024) Exploratory interviews with Flemish policy makers and academics on flood protection in the Sea Scheldt, and document analysis (both academic literature and grey literature)	Recordings of interviews; transcripts or minutes of recording; summaries and notes on document analysis	Audio- and Word-files	-	Not foreseen	(?)	until 2 years after the end of the project

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CS 5 (Western Scheldt, The Netherlands)	(Primary data collection) Interviews with policymakers, governmental organizations (across different layers of governance), NGOs, research institutes (e.g., Deltares), stakeholders' organizations (e.g., farmers, landowners) to understand to what extent and how the Dutch and Belgian partners aligns when it comes to flood risk management in the Western Scheldt. Secondary data collection through desk research.	Recordings of interviews, interview transcripts, summaries, minutes of meetings, documents, data analysis files (such as ATLAS TI).	Word, Audio, ATLAS TI files.	No.	Not foreseen yet.	Not determined yet.	To be defined in agreement with the consortium partners.
CS 6 (Oslofjord, Norway)	Exploratory and in-depth interviews with policymakers, governmental organizations (across different levels of governance), NGOs, research institutes, and other stakeholders to understand to what extent integrated land-sea planning is addressed in the Oslofjord, and how future effects of climate change is being addressed (e.g. increased precipitation) Secondary data collection through desk research.	Recordings of interviews; transcripts or minutes of recordings and meetings; summaries and notes on document analysis	Audio recordings, and word files	Yes, interview data from the CrossGov project	Not foreseen yet	Not determined yet.	To be defined in agreement with the consortium partners.
CS 7 (Canary Islands, Spain)	Exploratory interviews with local and regional policy makers, civil society, NGOs and academics on climate change impacts and governance (in coastal environments)	Interviews, questionnaires; summaries and notes on document analysis	Excel, word and PDFs	Official reports have been used to identify some risks: public documents	first approach to the project's focus groups, evaluation and impact assessment	Not determined yet.	until 2 years after the end of the project
CS 8 (Reunion, France)	unknow	unknow	unknow	unknow	unknow	unknow	unknow

Source: own elaboration

BlueGreen Governance **outputs and any associated data needs to be licensed** to permit the widest possible re-use.

For research outputs and data that BGG partners have full intellectual property right ownership, **the latest CC BY or CC 0 license shall be used**. For outputs such as peer reviewed publications, CC BY is recommended as it includes an attribution condition, where the authors must be given appropriate credit for the work if reused.

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UK Research and Innovation

BlueGreen Governance

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5. RESPONSABILITIES AND SECURITY

This DMP is managed through BlueGreen Governance Work Package 6. All BGG partners are responsible for engaging with the DMP with the goal of making BGG research inputs, throughputs and outputs open and publicly available as possible. Engagement with the DMP is bidirectional. Partners can give feedback, additional community/domain knowledge, additional requirements, etc., which will be reviewed and incorporated into the DMP as a living document. UV, in the role as a data steward, will provide support to partners regarding the practical implementation of the DMP. In particular, UV will provide training and support to assist in the uploading of metadata and data into Zenodo. This will include support for the quality review of metadata and data with the data owners within the consortium. UV will send periodic reminders to partners regarding uploading metadata and data.

Consequently, WP 6 will be in charge to upload the different DMP versions and every WP and CS's leaders will take care of the data creation and management process for their respective Work Packages and CS. All other consortium partners are committed to contribute to the data management as re-users, collectors and generators of data themselves. WP's and CS's leaders are also responsible for updating the different dataset versions of their findings and uses.

In terms of **security**, the conditions that will be fulfilled by BGG data are:

- Secure access to data

Data provided by research participants will be kept secured to prevent unauthorised access. In this regard, all datasets will be stored in drives that will require passwords to be accessed.

Data provided by research participants will be kept secured to prevent unauthorized access. In this regard, all datasets will be stored in drives that will require passwords to be accessed. Additional security measures include:

- Access Control: Only authorized personnel will have access to the data. Access rights will be reviewed and updated regularly to ensure that only current project members can access the data.
- Encryption: All sensitive data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest using industry-standard encryption protocols to prevent unauthorized access during data transfer and storage.
- Audit Trails: Maintaining detailed logs of all access and modification activities to data to monitor and identify any unauthorized access or suspicious activity.

- Secure storage

The BGG data will be stored in:

- Microsoft365 Teams Account: The use of a Microsoft365 Teams account will allow for secure collaboration and data sharing among project members. Data stored on Microsoft365 will be protected by the platform's security measures, including encryption, secure access controls, and regular backups.
- Backups: Regular backups will be made on secure external drives, which will also be encrypted and stored in a physically secure location or in secure cloud services like Google Drive or Dropbox Business, which comply with GDPR regulations.

- Sharing limitations

Only BGG researcher(s) will have access to physical documents and digital files. No data will be transferred to third parties without the consent of the research participant. Any use for commercial purposes is also formally excluded.

6. ETHICAL ASPECTS

The BGG project will collect or generate data from questionnaires, interviews, participatory workshops, discussions, reflection and learning sessions involving stakeholders and citizens that participate voluntarily in the project. The project will be collecting and processing personal data in these instances. How these data will be handled has been addressed at different points over the last sections of this DMP. All is collected in the current section.

Any data collection, processing and storage activities, procedures and tools in the project will be in line with the personal data protection and intellectual property rights of the European Union, as defined by the European Commission, and national legislation relevant to the country where the data collection is taking place. Data records containing personal data are managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679). ECS will not be collecting any 'special categories' of personal data as defined by Article 9 of the GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Formalised questionnaires and personal data will be stored at the local level.

A key element of sustainable data management, this DMP outlines what, and how, data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access and also how data will be curated and preserved during and after the end of the project. It provides guidelines, answers to issues, and presents the approach that the BGG project will adopt with respect to the management and protection of data. Legal and ethical issues related to the project's collecting and/or processing of personal data are identified and practically considered, taking into consideration in the different methods by which data are collected (interview, online survey, workshop, questionnaire, etc.).

The activities carried out in the framework of the BGG comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU and international legislation. Informed consent will be requested from all persons participating in the study, along with authorisation to publish the data, even if it is anonymised. The project will ensure that sensitive data will be anonymized when necessary.

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7. DATA MANAGEMENT AND NEW EU REGULATION

The push to harness the transformative potential of AI and automation is underway. AI technologies are increasingly applied to improve decision-making processes in a wide array of sectors, including those related to climate change risk management and prevention, as well as adaptation planning. However, amidst the global proliferation of AI in business and daily life, concerns about ethical use and risks emerge, with trust issues persisting under this rapidly evolving scenario.

To ensure that Europeans can benefit from these new technologies, in full respect of EU values and principles, the European Commission pledged to adopt a 'human-centric' approach to AI, and to address the risks associated with AI applications in its recent **EU AI Act on Artificial Intelligence**. The EU AI Act is a landmark piece of legislation that aims to regulate the use of AI within the European Union and is anticipated to set a new global standard for AI regulation. It represents a significant step towards ensuring that AI systems are developed and deployed in a way that is safe, ethical, and respects fundamental rights. The EU's AI Act aims to strike a delicate balance, fostering AI adoption, while upholding individuals' rights to responsible, ethical, and trustworthy AI use across multiple application domains. A risk-based approach is applied within the Act to safeguard fundamental rights, democracy, the rule of law, and environmental sustainability categorizing AI systems into 4 risk levels (i.e., from unacceptable, high, limited to minimal risk).

For **data management**, the implications of the EU AI Act are profound. High-risk AI systems, which include those that process large amounts of personal data, or are used in critical sectors, will be subject to stringent obligations. These obligations pertain to the quality of data, the transparency of algorithms, and the robustness of AI systems. Transparency in data management processes is vital for traceability. This means that entities must maintain clear records of data sources, processing methods applied, and decision-making pathways of AI systems to rebut any presumption of liability. On the other hand, data governance and management practices will need to be enhanced to ensure that the data feeding into AI systems is of high quality, which is essential for the safe performance and reliability of these systems. The EU AI Act's relationship with **data protection** law is also noteworthy. Given the broad definition of personal data under EU data protection laws, the development and use of AI systems will frequently result in the processing of personal data. The AI Act, at its core, is a product-safety law that provides for the safe technical development and use of AI systems, aligning with the principles of data protection. The Act emphasizes the importance of data privacy and protection. Entities must comply with existing regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) while handling personal data within AI systems.

The EU AI Act is set to reshape the landscape of AI application and data management in Europe. In the frame of data exploitation, assimilation, and development through AI-based modelling approaches, **BlueGreen Governance** recognizes the need to adapt its data management strategies to comply with the new regulations, ensuring that AI systems are not only cutting-edge and efficient but also trustworthy and respectful of individual rights and freedoms. Moreover, given that AI systems are not static and will evolve over time, a continuous monitoring and updating of both systems and the data they exploit will be applied during the project implementation, ensuring ongoing compliance with EU AI Act rules, as well as other directives or laws on this matter that could emerge during the project lifetime.

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In this setting, the project Coordinator together with WP Leaders must be proactive in timely identifying and addressing risks associated with data and modelling changes. In line with the EU AI Act rules, effective data management is at the heart of the BGG activities, serving as a safeguard against potential liabilities and fostering trust in AI technologies application within transformative CCA pathways.

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